

The Minimum Cell: criteria for minimum housing studies

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Abstract

The paper tries to define the necessary criteria to correctly analyze dwelling buildings with a social or subsidized background conceived during the XX century.

The defined criteria simultaneously allows the choice of the Housing Models, but also the definition of an 'Analysis Sheet' intended to give the necessary information about the Case-Studies' spatial distribution, areas, image and the author's intentions according to his current work and the Architectural Movement in which he operates.

The dweller is understood as an entity who as changed its aspirations and needs over time, thus becoming urgent the development of new housing proposals which allows the proper performance of the house's contemporary activities.

The obtained result throughout the Case-Studies analysis allows the determination of the validity or obsolescence of its formal, spacial and distributional contents during the specified period, in order to establish the basis of the design of new housing proposals which meet the needs on the common dweller.

Keywords: Housing; Dwelling; Space; Function; Criteria

1. Concept: the Minimum Cell

1.1 Definition

'The minimum volume of habitable space needed to implement all functional and social uses of their occupants'

1.1.1. Habitable Space

Defines the living space understood as 'home'. Inhabiting a space is not limited to the completion of practical tasks, but to the entire effort of ownership made by the occupant that manifest itself in many different fields. The 'culture' in which they operate determines the occupants use the space that becomes a Habitat. If eating is a basic human function, location, time and how it feeds the occupant is determined by cultural background. The habitat's 'container' – home – will express these cultural processes. Therefore being 'habitable' is not simply the ability to accommodate physical life, but also the capacity to support cultural and social life.

1.1.2. Minimum Volume

Defines the capacity of the three dimensional 'Habitable Space'. The notion of Minimum depends on many cultural factors. A family with a small income may arrange its smaller Habitable Space in a more rational way, but at the same time, its desire to create space for social parts may lead to the

adoption of inadequate furniture for the available area. A bourgeois family will connote a reduced ceiling height to 'social housing', preferring larger volumes, even if it does not pursue a real practical effect.

1.1.3. Functional Uses

Defines all the eminently practical activities that support physical life: eating, sleeping or using the toilet facilities. It should be noted that a merely functional activity is an abstraction: any human act, however unconscious it may seem, contains in itself a social and cultural meaning.

1.1.4. Social Uses

Defines all the socialization activities among dwellers (as a family or other) and also between dwellers and visitors, necessary activities to the development of the human mind.

- I. **Family:** Nuno Portas¹ refers the importance of the family's recognition based in the connection between class and way of life. He differentiates rural, worker and bourgeois backgrounds, in which the relationship among family members changes. The provider(s) vary according to his (her; their) background: just the father, father and mother and even the children. The private relationship among husband and wife, parents and their children and family and friends also varies according to their cultural origin. But the 'family' includes only part of the occupants of the home, since it implies kinship among inhabitants (even if we consider an extended family, with more members than those of the 'nuclear family'). Blood ties are not an exclusive for kinship definition, since it also implies by marriage and adopted relatives.
- II. **Household:** we must take in account other types of households, where 'housing cells', minimum or otherwise, are occupied with several people without any kind of kinship. 'Household' is a definition used in anthropological studies that contains a number of Types of dwellers, families included, that live in the same house. This is the basic criteria, but when there is more than one dweller it takes in account the activities that are performed in the same space, like meals. If cohabitation defines the Household, within this we can define multiple categories, where dwellers share the same age, occupation or financial status, none of this features necessarily simultaneous. Ana Isabel Afonso² prefers to use the definitions of 'nuclear, extended or composite households', instead of referring to 'family'. The variable need of intimacy manifest itself in a greater need to personalize the dwellers' private space(s).

1.2 Context

The 'cell' is intended as an abstract entity that is disconnected from its physical context. Consists in the set of relations among spaces destined to 'social and functional uses', according to the criteria defined by its author. It has a physical enclosure defined by outer walls, but limited to its immediate surroundings. It depends however on several other factors.

1.2.1 Building

The analysis of the 'cell' includes the study of external elements that participate on its definition. The way that those 'cells' associate themselves it's a factor that influences its accesses but also in the outer proportions of the 'cell' (and consequently, in the inner spaces distribution). So there will be some references made to certain characteristics that are motivated by accesses or construction techniques, although they won't be the object of a particular study

1.2.2 Urban Context

Pre-existences also determine the characterization of the 'cell', since they influence the building's configuration. Depth, height or shape of built of pre-existences are interfering situations that define the

¹ Portas, Nuno (2004) "*A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura*", 1st Edition, Porto: Edições FAUP
ISBN 972-9483-63-9

² Afonso, Ana Isabel (2004) "*Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas*", viewed in October 2008

<http://ceas.iscte.pt/etnografica/docs/vol_04/N1/Vol_iv_N1_153-182.pdf>

dwelling, since they oblige the use of different types of 'cells' according to light and airing needs, for example.

2. Criteria used in the case-studies' choice

2.1 'Cell'

The choice of the case studies will be determined by the definition of 'cell'. Our attention will be focused in the unit that supports the live of the household. Even if inserted in a larger group, the notion of 'unit' or 'cell' will prevail over other types.

2.1.1 Private or Collective

The definition of 'Collective Housing' is not an influential factor in the 'cell's' choice. The study of minimum cells, especially during the Modern Movement, was also made through the creation of isolated prototypes, not inserted in a major building. To limit our search to collective housing building would impoverish our research, since many interesting proposals would have to be ignored.

2.1.2 Communitarian or Individual

In the 'Collective Housing's definition is included the sharing of some spaces (like the plot or the accesses) and technical services that may not influence directly the definition of 'cell', but have some power over its configuration and internal spaces. The type of association of the 'cell' does not determine its choice, but must be referenced in its analysis.

2.1.3 Culture and Geography

In order to maintain some coherence in the criteria used in the 'cell's' analysis, models that come from particular cultures defined by very precise cultural and practical uses must be excluded, although we will not restrict our study to the boundaries of Europe.

- I. However the intention is not to produce a mere functional analysis, without paying attention to any kind of symbolism. The 'Material Culture'³ can't be isolated from its semiotic dimension: the dwelling's function is to be inhabited, but the way it is made it's the expression of a social dimension that is beyond practical aspects. Shape and organization may differ among the collected 'cells' due to different social behaviors, since the established relations between parents and children, or dweller and visitors, are manifested in how the different spaces are conceived and organized. For example, privacy is more valued in Southern Europe, who determines a greater attention voted to private spaces, especially if compared with Northern Europe.
- II. One of the main used sources is a book untitled 'Floor Plan Manual'⁴ since it mainly uses plans and sections as its primary means of communication and comparison of the collected housing proposals. Its importance is even recognized by Hilary French⁵, also the author a similar project, but recognizes that the main aim of the quoted book is to offer a general overview of contemporary housing and not to portray a particular movement or a trend: the author voluntarily limits his study to a field where are only small differences between culture and climate, thus limiting his research to Europe.

2.2 Minimum

The concept of 'Minimum Cell' is necessarily vague in certain parameters. The idea of a 'Minimum' was an evolutionary definition and sometimes contradictory, attached to the dominant architectural

³ **Bucaille, Ricard, Pesez, Jean-Marie** (1989) "*Cultura Material*", in **Ruggiero, Romano** (dir.), Enciclopédia Einaudi, vol. 16, Lisboa: Imprensa Nacional - Casa da Moeda
ISBN 972-270080-4

⁴ **Gänshirt, Christian** (dir.) (2007) 4th edition, "*Floor Plan Manual: Housing: 3. Updated and Extended*", Basel: Birkhäuser
ISBN-10 3764370351

⁵ **French, Hilary** (dir) (2008) "*Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century*", London: Laurence King Publishing Ltd
ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

movement or those opposed to its hegemony. As a reflection or antithesis of the society in which they are included, the 'Minimum Cell' has different criteria. Therefore it was chosen not to define precise rules, since there was the risk of excluding some important case-studies.

- I. If during the Modern Movement it was crucial to reduced the area of the minimum standards, in the Italian Neo-realism Movement gave more emphasis on offering bigger areas at the expense of some equipment and finishing details of the cell. Therefore, area can't be a determinant factor in the choice of the case-studies, as the 'minimum acceptable to life' does not depend on size or volume.

2.3 Costs

The building cost is a feature that is more influential in the idea of a 'minimum cell', since its research is in most cases related to mass production housing destined to less privileged populations. In the 'Modern Movement' the rationality of construction techniques and use of materials was a general concept for all architectural production, although they were (and are) mainly applied in subsidized and social housing.

2.3.1 Promoter

The main promoter of this type of housing is the country's government, due to the character of social responsibility associated to the right to decent housing. Since area is not a determinant feature in the definition of a 'minimum cell', the State as a promoter substitutes, in general, this criteria in the choice of case-studies, since its housing projects are directly linked to the principles that define an efficient 'minimum cell'.

2.3.2 Investigation

This kind of promotion is often related to housing policies that endorse spatial and constructive experimentation laboratories, trough mass construction often linked to a specific architectural trend. As a reflection of the valid theories in a precise timeline, social housing programs are valid criteria in choosing case-studies.

2.4 Experimentation

The effort put in use in the investigation and experiment of innovative proposals of housing cells is also a used criteria. Architectural quality is a very broad definition, and its importance is also variable according to author and period of the project (assuming the co-relation established among creator and society, individual and collective).

2.4.1 Icons

The need for a consensual opinion about 'architectural quality' leads to the choice of architecture 'masters' (as defined by critics in general) whose work will be chosen as mirror of the Architectural Movement in which they operate.

2.4.2 Forgotten authors

Despite the attempts to unify theory and practice in some architectural movements, it is considered that hegemony was never achieved. Architects always applied in their work a personal touch that distinguished them from the trend to which they are commonly associated. That character was often the reason why some of them were often forgotten by the architectural critique and orthodox History. That doesn't indicate a lesser quality job, only that even the more important trend in architecture is also made of different types of gray. This is why lesser known architectures are also chosen to participate in this study.

2.5 Sources

It seems somewhat contradictory to research for Models of 'minimum cells' in documentary sources, since the publication of a project or an author implies it and his recognition by the architectural community. This recognition, however, was made in a precise moment that may not be our present time. And today that model and that author may be forgotten but still valid to Architecture History.

2.5.1 Date

The chosen source assumes its importance trough the date of publication versus the date of the project. From all the projects once published, present time only uses certain examples, in most cases from the

'Masters'. As far as possible, to search for models published in their own time reveals to be most important because it will symbolizes architectural practice in its time. Contemporary recollections will remain important because they also establish the importance of the included Models, comparatively to its predecessor's publications.

2.5.2 The Source's Author

The main responsible for a publication also indirectly defines the importance or oblivion of a Model or an Architect, since they applied their own personal criteria in the selection of the case-studies. So, the illustration of a particular time and space will also be the illustration of the author's time and space. A small investigation about the book authors will be made in order to understand what dictates or dictated his choices.

2.6 Typology

Some definitions must be made clear before we proceed, like the definition of 'Model', 'Type' and 'Typology'. Anthony Vidler⁶ tries to accomplish consensus in this matter. Using previous studies he achieves a definition of 'Type' that excludes merely physical aspects. The 'Type' is therefore a set of physical and ideological features through which we can group a whole range of 'case-studies', similar according to the predefined characteristics. The 'case-studie' it is called 'Model' that, unlike the 'Type', is a concrete example. The study that groups the 'Models' according to their 'Type' it's called 'Typology'.

Therefore the 'Type' defined by the number of bedrooms (referred as T_x , being the x the variable corresponding to the number of rooms) also can determine the choice of different 'Models'. If we pretend to make a comparison among the collected 'cells' it's important that they have some elements in common, as it was explained before.

2.6.1 Bedrooms

For instance, the same number of rooms in different 'cells' allows comparisons among them, through the areas they spend in communal or private spaces. It's also necessary to focus our attention in the typologies that are more common, but also more interesting in spatial terms. However the proportion among 'Types' is also dictated by different demands: in post-catastrophe periods the preference goes to the 'Types' that allow its occupation by complete families, in times of prosperity Studios and T1's are preferred, given the (financial) opportunity to live alone. Therefore the selection of 'Models' also takes in account the social and economic context.

2.6.2 Capacity

Due to different 'spatial cultures' among countries, or even different regulations, it is avoided to use the designation T_x/y , where the y stands for the 'maximum capacity'⁷ of the 'cell', or the maximal number of tenants it allows. This classification consists already in an analysis, which will be avoided when choosing the 'case-studies'

- I. The maximum capacity of the 'cell' is, however, used by Alexander Klein⁸ as a criteria to define the quality of a dwelling: the '*betteffekt*' is the ratio between the number of beds and the floor area, meaning that for a better value, a bedroom for two beds had to be slightly bigger than one for just one bed.

⁶ Vidler, Anthony (1977) "*The Third Typology*", in *Architecture Theory since 1968* (1998), New York: Columbia Books of Architecture ISBN 0-262-58188-4

⁷ Pedro, João Branco (2001) 4th edition "*Programa Habitacional – Habitação, ICT Informação Técnica Arquitectura ITA5*", Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil ISBN 972-49-1812-2

⁸ Klein, Alexander (1980) "*Vivienda Mínima: 1906 – 1957*", Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, pp. 88

3. Case-studies' designing criteria

3.1 Reproduction

The 'cell' will be reproduced from the paper or digital source without changes, exceptions made under the following circumstances:

3.1.1 Measurement corrections

Some measurements seem incoherent, sometimes originated by the imprecision of the source. There will be no corrections made because it is fundamental to be faithful to one's source. These inaccuracies can arise from unknown or less obvious constraints of the project, for example:

- I. Peculiar plot dimensions.
- II. A particular geometrical system used by the architect or imposed by general legislation.
- III. The use of different measurement units.

3.1.2 Quality of the reproductions

The lack of quality of the reproductions present in some sources makes some drawings inaccurate, even if digitalized through a scanner and drawn with the help of CAD (Computer Assisted Design). The thickness and irregularity of the lines of the drawing is one example, which may misinform.

- I. Therefore there will be defined two midpoints at the beginning and at the end of the line, which will determine the location of the correct original line.
- II. The irregularity of the lines will not be incorporated in the final design, but major corrections will be avoided.

3.1.3 Exclusion criteria

The 'migration' of the (designed or constructed) original project to an architectural publication or other kind of source may lead to inconsistencies that are impossible to verify. If the selected model as a number of irregularities that call into question its credibility, the 'cell' will be excluded from the present study.

3.2 Design standardization

In order to make the models easier to compare, some amendments are necessary. The purpose is to facilitate the appreciation of the project without calling into question the integrity of the original design.

3.2.1 Bathroom/toilet ware

In some models the drawing that represents the toilet ware is an incoherent drawing in its representation or measurements. Therefore it will be adopted a number of symbols, representing toilet, bidet and washbasin that will become an empiric measurement method, common to all the designed models. The same will be applied in kitchen ware, where the stove and the washbasin will have the same symbol.

Exceptions will be made in the showers, bathtubs and, occasionally, the washbasin because they are often adapted to a space or a niche in particular, without standard measurements. Also, the models that are further apart in time (XVIII or XIX century) didn't have toilets or bathrooms in the way we are accustomed to imagine them.

3.2.2 Furniture

Some sources include in the design of the models some furniture symbols which seek to explain the use of a certain space or area, sometimes by the author's will, others by the publisher's will. Every so often these symbols try to explain additional uses, most likely included in the original drawings. The Voldparken project (1951), Husum, Denmark, by Kay Fisker (1893-1965) features a dashed line that converts a sofa into a bed. The rooms are not fit for a double bed, so it's possible that the architect intended the conversion of the living room into a bedroom by night. Hence the importance of the furniture symbols seen in the original drawings in explaining the envisioned uses of spaces.

Voldparken (1951), Kay Fisker (1893-1965)

Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner, 1992, "*Viviendas en bloques alineados*", Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A., pp. 65

ISBN 968-887-186-9

The use of furniture symbols also offers the additional purpose of providing scale to the drawing, but it will be avoided the 'decoration' of the house plan with an unlimited set of pieces of furniture: there will be a limited number of symbols representing the more common pieces: sofas, dining table and beds, which provide an immediate caption of a room.

There are some specific Architectural Movements or authors that use these symbols with a more specific intention, like Alexander Klein (1879-1961) who defined the specific place for each piece of furniture in order to make the space more functional, even in terms of sun exposure.

When furniture is not originally represented, it will be included in the redesign of the 'cell', in order to unify and visually scale the drawing, using the above mentioned symbols.

3.2.3 House plan

According to the same effort to standardize the design of the 'cells' it was defined an overall image that will be repeated in each case studie. Apart from the above mentioned symbols, all the walls will be represented in gray, regardless of how it is presented in the source.

3.3 Captions

In order to maintain the same uniformity criteria, the use of captions aims the immediate recognition of the cell plan. Depending on the source and the principles adopted, the captions may be more or less generic: in some cases a living area and a dining area are indicated in the same space, in others the same space it is referred as a 'communal room'. In others situations there is an empirical recognition of the spaces and uses (without captions). Symbols as the ones adopted to indicate the entrance of the cell will also be uniformed.

Prototype (?), Alexander Klein (1879-1961)

Klein, Alexander, 1980, "*Vivienda Mínima, 1906 – 1957*", Barcelona, Gustavo Gili, pp. 149

3.3.1 Rule

Since it is intended to include the cell in a case-study file, where the analysis will be based, its drawing cannot consist itself in a comment or analysis. Therefore, the adopted captions must be 'harmless', in order not to interpret the referred spaces.

3.3.2 Exceptions

In 'cells' where rooms have no physical boundaries the captions have to be more specific. An open kitchen/dining/living room can cause some confusion: if we identify the dining area as a part of the kitchen, we are already making a judgement about the functional aspects of the house and its users. Also, in the Functionalist Movement these areas were defined, if not through walls, by the relation establish among rooms (dining areas near the kitchen, living spaces hereafter the dining room, etc.)

3.3.4 Examples of application of the parameters

Bad Dürrenberg, apartamento C2, (1930), Alexander Klein (1879-1961)

Klein, Alexander, 1980, "*Vivienda Mínima, 1906 – 1957*", Barcelona, Gustavo Gili, pp. 149

'Cell' in Brussels (undated; presented at CIAM II), unknown author
Aymonino, Carlo, 1973, *'La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930'* Barcelona: Gustavo Gili

Forte Quezzi,(1968), Luigi Carlo Daneri (1900-1972)
Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner, 1992, *"Viviendas en bloques alineados"*, Barcelona: Gustavo Gili, pp. 149
ISBN 968-887-186-9

4 Case studies

Chamberlin, Powell and Bon **GOLDEN LANE ESTATE** 1952

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Outside Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Living/Dining Room
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - Bathroom
- 8 - Bedroom

Scala 1/200

Project		GOLDEN LANE ESTATE		
Location	London (United Kingdom)			
Author	Chamberlin, Powell e Bom			
Date	1952			
Promoter	Public (for City workers)			
Association of the cell	Free-standing structure			
Access	Outside Corridor			
Type	T2 e T3			
TYPE-APARTMENT		Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type		T2		
Total Area	72,9			
Usable Area	59,1		91,5%	
Public Spaces				
Living/Dining Room	18,6	76,9%	31,5%	
(balcony)	5,8		8,0%	
Kitchen	5,6	23,1%	9,5%	
(cabinet)	1,1	19,6%		
(counter)	2,3	41,1%		
Total	24,2	100,0%	40,9%	
Private Spaces				
Bedroom	11,8	50,2%	20,0%	
(closet)	1,1	9,3%		
Bedroom	11,7	49,8%	19,8%	
(balcony)	1,8		2,5%	
(closet)	1,1	9,4%		
Total	23,5	100,0%	39,8%	
Other Areas				
Bathroom	3,3		5,6%	
Hall	2,1	25,9%	3,6%	
Stairs	3,2	39,5%	5,4%	
Corridor	2,8	34,6%	4,7%	
(closet)	0,4	14,3%		
Total	8,1	100,0%	13,7%	
Total (closet/cabinet space)	3,7		6,3%	
Total Usable Area	59,1		100,0%	
Total (balconies)	7,8		10,4%	

original drawing:

<http://www.building.co.uk/story.asp?sectioncode=655&storycode=313386&c=3>
[04-2009]

<http://www.exhibit-goldenlane.com/2008/07/10/259/>
[04-2009]

association of the cell:

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1952 **GOLDEN LANE ESTATE** Chamberlin, Powell and Bon

GOLDEN LANE ESTATE 1952

'New Hall College, Cambridge' 1962-66
http://www.vitruvius.com.br/arquitextos/arq047/arq047_01_e.asp [04.2009]

Small areas, yet 'spacious-looking'¹
 Double-height living room and elegant stairs
 Window between the kitchen and living room
 Also a double-height balcony
 Reminiscences of Le Corbusier's Housing Units

Common in duplexes, the distribution of area between public and private sectors comes from the separation by floors
 Rooms with generous areas with almost 12m²
 Living room with 'only' 19m² and a 'functionalist' kitchen with 5.6m²
 Although open, the space under the stairs is not usable

Given the small areas, there is a concern with storage spaces
 Kitchen, corridor and bedrooms with closets

CHAMBERLIN, POWELL & BON

1920 – 1999 (Geoffrey Chamberlin); 1919 – 1978 (Peter 'Joe' Powell); 1919 – 1978 (Christoph Bom)

'Barbican Estate' 1965-76
<http://www.flickr.com/photos/suburbanance/1697819929/> [04.2009]

British architects and teachers

Society created for development of the 1st award winning Golden Lane Estate project
 They all individually competed, but had agreed to jointly develop the winning design

Regarded as the first representatives of British Modernism
 Although they are also considered as 'brutalistas'
 The use of concrete, present in the Barbican Estate, must have greatly contributed

Very influenced by the ideas of Le Corbusier
 Their urban planning concept was close to the 'Ville Radieuse'
 The Golden Lane planning, a urban microcosm with all the necessary infrastructures, born in a war destroyed space, has a lot in common
 There are also comparisons between the Golden Lane 'duplexes' and Le Corbusiers' Unité d'Habitation cells
 The positioning of the staircase and high ceilings are similar to Nantes

The influence of 'Architectural Review' magazine from the 40 / 50s is also strong
 Dominated by a group of artists led by Gordon Cullen, a great proponent of the concept of 'Townscape' through publishing
 Is the art of making the maze of buildings, streets and spaces that make up the urban environment visually coherent and organized²

Architecture teachers at the Polytechnic of Kingston, later university

¹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Golden_Lane_Estate, [04.2009]
² http://www.almedina.net/catalog/product_info.php?products_id=4428, [04.2009]

For each of the collected models it will be made a case-study sheet, intended to serve as basis for further analysis, gathering for this purpose as much information as possible.

4.1 Header

Project	FORSHAGAGATAN
Location	Farsta (Sweden)
Author	Nils Lonnroth
Data	1959
Promoter	unknown
Association of the cells	4 storey block
Accesses	Two apartments per floor
Type	T2

The header consists of various information which may be defined as technical data. The information is general, but influences, even if indirectly, the composition of the 'cell'.

4.1.1 Name of the project

The designation is selected according to the source, and fully reproduced. The criteria chosen by it to identify a project is not always the same: it may consist in the name of the street in which the building stands, the name of the promoting programme or even the name given by its author. In other cases, History itself is responsible for christening the building. However, if one favours one source to reproduce the plan of the 'cell', then he must use the applied designation.

4.1.2 Location

Defined by the district/village/town/city and country in which the building stands. The precision of this indication is variable according to the source.

4.1.3 Author

It refers author of the project. The use of the designation 'architect' would not be accurate since some authors don't have architectural training, and others have training in other disciplines.

4.1.4 Date

It is common to present only one reference (a year) without specifying a phase (design/construction/completion). Other sources present two dates according to the interval between the designing of the building and its completion.

When only one date is presented, it is assumed that it is referred to the beginning of the designing process. When two dates are present, only the first one is considered in order to establish a chronologic chart of all the collected 'cells'.

4.1.5 Promoter

The majority of the selected models makes part of a subsidized public program (one of the criteria defined for choosing the 'cells'). In some cases the source only indicates if it is 'public housing', but in others the 'program' is specified. However, private housing or from an unknown promoter are not excluded.

4.1.6 Association

Although it is not a fundamental parameter in the choice of the 'cell', it influences its shape and spatial contents. There are many designations who define the type of the association, sometimes the same type. So, the way the source defines the association of the 'cells' it is used as a reference: block, tower, row housing, etc.

4.1.7 Accesses

A block doesn't always imply the same type of access: it may be a stairway enclosure, an open gallery, etc. Other cases use more than one single way of access. Like the association, the access also determines the physical and spatial aspects of the 'cell', through the different relations that are established between outer and inner spaces, and the way these are distributed. Again, it is taken into account the way the source defines the access.

4.1.8 Typology

The above outlined criteria will be use, according to the formula Tx, where 'x' is the variable number of bedrooms. The number of occupants of each room will not be defined, since it depends of several factors, including regulations or the architect's ideology.

4.2 Technical elements

STANDARD CELL	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T3		
Gross Floor Area	97,3		
Floor Area	73,9		80,6%

The intention is to cross-reference information about the 'cell' relating, for instance, the area of each room to the total area of the house.

4.2.1 Elements of the 'Cell'

Here are included some items that do not fit in the header, which is referred to the building in general, and not to the 'cell'. By 'standard cell' it is identified that the case-studie refers to the more common cell in the building, but it may also indicate a special situation (gable, corner, etc.).

Gross Floor Area (cell): João Branco Pedro⁹ says that it 'is measured through the external contour of the exterior walls of the building and annexes, or through the axis of the walls that separate the house'. This definition does not take into account the communal areas of the total dwellers, including accesses. It is intended a comparison among the different spaces that organize the 'cell'. Including spaces that are not exclusive to it would be illogical. External private spaces are taken into account, according to the definition above, like balconies, verandas and patios.

Floor Area (cell): Nuno Portas¹⁰ defines it as 'the measurement by the inner perimeter of the interior walls (...)'. João Branco Pedro defines it as 'the floor area of a compartment, including closets, minus (...) the areas where the ceiling is lower than regulated'. As such, the usable area of the 'cell' will be the sum of the floor area of all its compartments.

Area (cell): the concept of 'Area' is different from 'Floor Area', which is defined by Nuno Portas as the 'sum of the floor area with the area of the balconies. The percentage expressed in the lower right corner (80,6%) refers to the proportion between 'area' and 'gross floor area', where, in the example above, the 'area' corresponds to 80,6% of the 'gross floor area': the remaining 19,4% consists on walls and other infrastructures.

Area of the balconies: according to Nuno Portas it is 'the not enclosed area in direct communication with house and for its exclusive use'. This will be accounted in accordance with the room that it serves (balcony of the kitchen, of the lounge, etc.).

⁹ **Pedro, João Branco** (2002) "*Programa Habitacional – Espaços e Compartimento, ICT Informação Técnica Arquitectura ITA4*", Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, 3rd edition
ISBN 972-49-1811-4

¹⁰ **Portas, Nuno** (1969) "*Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação, Informação Técnica: Edifícios*", Lisbon, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil

4.2.2 Zone definition

When defining inner spaces with similar uses it was chosen to employ a generic definition. The spaces that are commonly used by the household (communal areas), are distinguished from those generally used by their specific occupants (private areas).

When trying to define the parameters that programmatic spaces must comply within the 'cell', Nuno Portas chooses to classify them through their functional aspects. He doesn't define a physical limit for a specific area, but determines several activities that take place in a house: 1) sleep, rest; 2) meal preparation; 3) casual and formal meals, among other categories. Nevertheless this kind of analysis does not suit to the present investigation. The inexistence of a physical boundary and the shared spaces of the various activities prevent a clear overview of the various 'cells'.

It is also avoided a differentiation like the one proposed by the CIAM (International Congress of Modern Architecture), in which the public and private areas were complemented with purely technical spaces, like the kitchen or the bathrooms¹¹. It is nowadays commonly accepted that a kitchen, for instance, has a very important socio-cultural aspect that allows its use as a space for social and leisure activities.

Therefore, the chosen categories will be the following: household's 'public areas', 'private areas' and 'other areas' (where are included spaces that do not belong in the previous categories and do not define new categories for themselves).

Within those categories the usages that may be performed in a physically defined space will be distinguished in a generalist way: living room, kitchen, bedroom, bathroom, etc. Sometimes it can also appear: office, multipurpose rooms or separated usages in the bathroom (like the toilet separated from the rest of the bathroom).

4.2.3 Household's public areas

It will be taken into account, partially, the definition given by João Branco Pedro: living/dining rooms, kitchen and sometimes a bathroom. He defines 'communal' a space which everybody has access for functional and emotional needs. The bathroom won't be considered a private area, because there are no user's intentional traces, like those left in a private bedroom. In some case-studies the kitchen, very small (sometimes for ideological reasons) doesn't allow a simultaneous use, so it can't be considered a real communal space. So it will be used the following definitions:

4.2.4 Private areas

João Branco Pedro uses the expression 'individual spaces' that comprises bedrooms and possibly a bathroom (in a suite bedroom, possibly, or when there are two bathrooms). However classifying those as 'individual' seems to excuse a bedroom used by siblings, who appropriate space differently from a couple. It is therefore preferred the term 'private', since it doesn't imply a number of users.

Bedrooms: associated commonly only with sleeping (a very 'Modernist' definition), but also used as a play area or study. Changing lifestyles and increasing financial status imply nowadays the presence of computers, stereos or televisions.

An office also can be considered as a private space, but it can support a professional activity where guests are welcomed. Therefore, as the multipurpose areas, they are considered as public areas.

4.2.5 Another areas

There are several reasons why certain spaces are not included in the above categories. Some are purely functional, like a closet room or a corridor. Another reason is the analysis made in the case study charts, where the relation between public and private is very important: if the bathrooms were added to same category of living rooms and kitchens we would be led to believe that the household's public spaces were wider than they really are.

Bathrooms: there are some discussions about the inclusion of this space as public or private. It is true that dwellers don't use it as a living space, but all of them have access to it. The Existenzminimum

¹¹Aymonino, Carlo, 1973, "La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930", Barcelona: Gustavo Gili
ISBN 84-252-0755-X

considered them as technical spaces, Nuno Portas defines them as private and João Branco Pedro makes a distinction between public bathrooms and private in-suite bathrooms.

Lobby and corridors: these definitions and spaces sometimes overlap since both are neutral spaces that distribute the dwellers within the house. And also, corridors may serve as lobbies and vice versa. Therefore those designations will be used only when their characteristics are clear, so the more wide-ranging designation of 'distribution' will be used in other circumstances.

Dens: their existence sometimes depends on the organization of the 'cell', but there are also some cultural issues that determine their presence, like in the Italian Neo-realism.

4.3 Spread sheet

The spread sheet is organized in three columns that gather information on the areas described above, but also about other spaces on the dependence of those.

	Area (m ²)	Zone	Total
Public areas			
Lounge	23,1	87,8%	31,3%
(balcony)	4,5		
Kitchen	3,2	12,2%	4,3%
(counter)	1,7	53,1%	
Total	26,3	100,0%	35,6%

4.3.1 Area (m²)

In here are reported the values of the floor area (in square meters) of each of the spaces that compose the 'cell'. Those are grouped by categories: 'public areas', 'private areas' and 'other areas'; in the last category the total sum of the areas of the rooms is not calculated, only on its subcategories.

In this parameter it is also made the sum of all the storage areas recorded during the process, including incorporated closets in bedrooms, lobby and dens.

At the bottom of the column it is showed the total floor area, or the sum of all the categories described.

Outras Zonas			
WC	2,2	25,0%	3,1%
Bathroom	6,6	75,0%	9,2%
Toilet Total	8,8	100,0%	12,2%
Lobby	2,6	63,4%	3,6%
(closet)	0,3	11,5%	
Corridor	1,5	36,6%	2,1%
Circulation Total	4,1	100,0%	5,7%
Den	1,3		1,8%
Storage Total	1,6		2,2%
Floor Area Total	72,0		100,0%

In each individual space it is noted the area of wardrobes, counters or other kind of built-in furniture. Its area is included in the floor area of the room. Balconies and patios are also taken in consideration, but this time their area is not included in the room (since they are outer spaces, not inner floor area)

		Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Public Areas				
Lounge		23,1	87,8%	31,3%
	(balcony)	4,5		
Kitchen		3,2	12,2%	4,3%
	(counter)	1,7	53,1%	
Total		26,3	100,0%	35,6%

4.3.2 Zone

These values are presented in percentage and correspond to the proportion between a room and the 'area' in which is included: 'private areas', 'public areas' or 'other areas' (in the following the area of the lounge corresponds to 75.9% of the 'public areas').

		Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Public Areas				
Lounge		20,2	75,9%	37,1%
	(balcony)	7,4		
Kitchen		6,4	24,1%	11,7%
	(counter)	1,6	25,0%	
Total		26,6	100,0%	48,8%

The sum of all the percentages of a certain 'area' must correspond to 100%. Wardrobes and counters are also presented in percentage, but now they estimate the proportion between their area and the area of the room (for instance, the kitchen counter corresponds to 25% of the floor area of the kitchen).

		Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Public Areas				
Lounge		20,2	75,9%	37,1%
	(balcony)	7,4		
Kitchen		6,4	24,1%	11,7%
	(counter)	1,6	25,0%	
Total		26,6	100,0%	48,8%

4.3.3 Total

This percentage corresponds to the relation between the area of a room and the floor area of the 'cell' (the area of the lounge corresponds to 37.1% of the total floor area, per example).

These percentages are also summed up, partially (per Zone) and totally: here their total has to be 100%.

All the storage space is also summed up and its percentage is also calculated (the storage space corresponds to 6.6% of the floor area of the 'cell').

	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Other Areas			
Storage Total	4,2		6,6%

After the Floor Area total of the 'cell' appears the sum of all the balconies and patios. Based on this we calculate the percentage of the outdoor spaces in the Gross Floor Area of the 'cell'. Based on this value it is calculated the relation (in percentage) between Area and Gross Floor Area (the outer spaces account for 13.1% of the Gross Floor Area, and the sum of the Floor Area and Outer Areas corresponds for 79.6% of the Gross Floor Area).

TYPE APARTMENT	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T3		
Gross Floor Area	61,0		
Floor Area	40,6		79,6%
Total de Área Útil	40,6		100,0%
Outer Spaces Total	8,0		13,1%

4.4 Information Column

To the right of the spreadsheet and the header there is available a range of information destined to complement the previous. According to the available space, these elements can also arise under the captions. It is more general information, not referring to the 'cell' in particular, but to the building, its surroundings, etc.

4.4.1 Original Floor Plan Drawing

The intended uniformity among drawings it is useful and necessary, but it is important to present the original drawings, even if without a proper scale (most of the times smaller than the used 1/200).

As in a written source, the drawn elements also need references. That makes possible to verify the fidelity of the re-worked floor plan. Referring these drawings as 'originals' is avoided on purpose, since, for example, in book used as a source, they have been in most cases already redesigned. This is

the case of 'Viviendas en Bloques Alineados'¹² (drawn by hand) or 'Key Urban Housing'¹³ (drawn in CAD) but not of 'Floor Plan Manual'¹⁴ (reproducing integrally the original drawings, regardless if by hand or by CAD) or 'Modern Housing Prototypes'¹⁵ (reproducing the original handmade drawings).

In an additional file, designated as 'Extra Sources' are presented further bibliographic data or internet sites where the mentioned project can be consulted and used to cross-check information among different sources.

4.4.2 Photos of the project

Whenever possible it will be included some photos of the 'cell' or the building in which they belong. This is a variable parameter since in some case, due to the age of the project there are no photos or even drawings available.

4.4.3 Association of the 'Cells'

It will be made a small reference to the way the 'cells' are put together, in which the case studie will be marked.

4.4.4 Source abbreviation

The source/publication of the 'cell' is identified trough an abbreviation of its name (two, three or four letters):

VBA: '*Viviendas en Bloques Alineados*', 1992, Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. [ISBN 968-887-186-9]

6YH: '*6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition*', W. W. Norton & Company, New York, 2000 [ISBN 0-393-73052-2]

The decoding of these abbreviations is included in a file where some information is gathered about the authors.

With this code is presented the page where the project can be found. In some cases it is necessary to crosscheck more than one source, so both abbreviations and pages will be presented.

4.5 Distributive scheme

Using color schemes and arrows, it is tried to clarify the relationship established among the various spaces that compose the 'cell'.

4.5.1 Coloring

The 'private areas' and the 'public areas' are assigned a particular color each, but for 'other areas' the option was to separate bathrooms from halls and corridors. It is easier this way to get a more direct understanding of the connected spaces (public, private, and bathroom) and connecting spaces (hall and corridor). The balconies and patios also have a distinctive color.

4.5.2 Distribution

Through a system of arrows, information is added to the color scheme: it is now clarified the connection among the rooms of the 'cell', along with

French, Hilary - *Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century*, 2008
Laurence King Publishing Ltd
ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

Núcleo INA-Casa (1953),
Giancarlo De Carlo

¹² Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner (1992) "*Viviendas en bloques alineados*", Barcelona: Gustavo Gili
ISBN: 968-887-186-9

¹³ French, Hilary (2008) "*Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century*", Laurence King Publishing
ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

¹⁴ Gänshirt, Christian (coordinator) (2007) "*Floor Plan Manual: Housing: 3. Updated and Extended*", Basel: Birkhäuser,
ISBN-10: 3764370351

¹⁵ Roger Sherwood (2002) "*Modern Housing Prototypes*", Harvard Paperbacks
ISBN-10: 0674579429; ISBN-13: 9780674579422

their relative line-up. The system starts at the main door entrance, and here it is a public route, since dwellers and visits both use it. The public route serves the 'public areas' but also the bathrooms, even if they stand among the bedrooms: once again, a visit could have access to it. The private route serves bedrooms and other possible private spaces. Finally, the external route gives access to balconies and patios. Sometimes rooms have more than one access, so the circulation scheme becomes circular. The orientation of the arrow is arbitrary and it doesn't mean a compulsory course.

Mannheimer Strasse
(1960), Oswald Mathias Ungers

4.6 Preliminary analysis

Here are underlined some distinguishable features of the studied 'cell'. There will be made some brief notes, without a specific order or criteria about its common and exceptional features. Since there is already a space for pictures of the project, the left space of the 'preliminary analysis' is used to present some of the author's other projects or works.

VOLDPARKEN

1951

Vestersøhus, 1939

No apparent hierarchy

Public and private are not separated, physically and ideologically
One corridor serves both 'public areas' and 'private areas'

Spaces are easy to appropriate

The lounge can also be used as a master bedroom
The kitchen may have a dining area, if necessary
Bedroom by the entrance may have also a public function as an office

Imbalance in the distribution of areas between public and private

More than one half of the floor area is public space, so it can provide the double function lounge mentioned above
Very small bedroom, incapable of accommodate a double bed (another reason for the lounge/bedroom)
Distribution spaces account for 11% of the total floor area

4.7 Biography

Some knowledge about the author's ideas and artistic context is very important for the analysis of the 'cell'. Here it is made a review of his (hers) life and work, were the more important features will be stressed. Their age and the fact that they might not be the best known authors of their time can make the information gathering a very difficult task, sometimes without any results. However even a small reference in the corner of a page might be informative, so this cannot be considered a useless effort.

JOSEP EMILI DONATO 1932 – ...

Spanish painter, architect and urban planner

Studied Fine Arts, who influenced its perception of Architecture

Made some travels in order to get to know the buildings mentioned in his architectural studies

His architecture is manifested as the demand for a formal plasticity

Its manifested trough the intelligent use of materials and technique

Considers however that the 'drawing, more than a word, is like a caricature (...) of the final object'¹⁶

His architecture is based on the expression of timeless forms and aesthetics

'The novelty is not a novelty'¹⁷, which means that vanguard is not synonymous of quality

Expresses monumentality in his works, which he considers inherent to its public nature

His material of choice is red brick

His choice, however, is dictated by the economic imperatives of the project: different circumstances leads to different materials

Also works as architectural critic and teacher

Commissioner of Culture at the College of Architects

Professor at the Polytechnic University of Catalonia

Mgazine director 'Cuadernos de Arquitectura y Urbanismo'

Tries to understand the cultural and social fabric in which architecture is performed.

References

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Bucaille, Ricard, Pesez, Jean-Marie (1989) *‘Cultura Material’*, in **Ruggiero, Romano** (dir.), Enciclopèdia Einaudi, vol. 16, Lisboa: Imprensa Nacional - Casa da Moeda, ISBN 972-270080-4

Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner (1992), *‘Viviendas en bloques alineados’*, Barcelona: Gustavo Gili, ISBN: 968-887-186-9

¹⁶ <<http://www.vitruvius.com.br/resenhas/textos/resenha032.asp>>, accessed in October 2008

¹⁷ <<http://www.geocities.com/medit1976b/donato2.htm>>, accessed in October 2008

French, Hilary (dir) (2008) *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, London: Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

Gänshirt, Christian (dir.) (2007) 4th edition, *'Floor Plan Manual: Housing: 3. Updated and Extended'*, Basel: Birkhäuser, ISBN-10 3764370351

Klein, Alexander (1980) *'Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957'*, Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, pp. 88

Pedro, João Branco (2001) 4th edition *"Programa Habitacional – Habitação, ICT Informação Técnica Arquitectura ITA5"*, Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, ISBN 972-49-1812-2

Pedro, João Branco (2002), *"Programa Habitacional – Espaços e Compartimento, ICT Informação Técnica Arquitectura ITA4"*, Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, 3rd edition, ISBN 972-49-1811-4

Portas, Nuno (1969), *"Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação, Informação Técnica: Edifícios"*, Lisbon, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil

Portas, Nuno (2004) *"A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura"*, 1st Edition, Porto: Edições FAUP, ISBN 972-9483-63-9

Roger Sherwood, 2002, *'Modern Housing Prototypes'*, Harvard Paperbacks, ISBN-10: 0674579429; ISBN-13: 9780674579422

Vidler, Anthony (1977) *'The Third Typology'*, in *Architecture Theory since 1968* (1998), New York: Columbia Books of Architecture, ISBN 0-262-58188-4

Web Page:

Afonso, Ana Isabel (2004) *'Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas'*, viewed in October 2008
<http://ceas.iscte.pt/etnografica/docs/vol_04/N1/Vol_iv_N1_153-182.pdf>

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Staircase
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Balcony
- 5 - Toilet
- 6 - Shower
- 7 - Bedroom
- 8 - Lounge

Scale

1/200

Project **OVERSCHIE**

Location Rotterdam
 Author Jacob B. Bakema e Joahannes H. van den Broek
 Date 1957
 Promoter unmentioned

Association of the cell Aligned Block
 Acessos Common staircase
 Type T2

original drawing:

TYPE-APARTMENT	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T2		
Gross Floor Area	66,3		
Floor Area	53,0		83,0%
Public Spaces			
Lounge	18,6	79,8%	35,1%
(closet)	0,4	2,2%	
Kitchen	4,7	20,2%	8,9%
(balcony)	2,0		3,0%
(counter)	1,5	31,9%	
Total	23,3	100,0%	44,0%
Private Spaces			
Bedroom	8,7	42,6%	16,4%
Bedroom	11,7	57,4%	22,1%
Total	20,4 *	100,0%	38,5%
Other Areas			
Bedroom Sink	0,5	12,8%	0,9%
Bedroom Sink	0,5	12,8%	0,9%
Toilet	0,9	23,1%	1,7%
Shower	2,0	51,3%	3,8%
Total	3,9	100,0%	7,4%
Hall	5,4		10,2%
(closet)	1,6	29,6%	
Usable Area Total	53,0		100,0%

* the area occupied by the sink it is not taken into account

Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner
 "Viviendas en bloques alineados", 1992,
 Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A.
 ISBN 968-887-186-9

association of the cell:

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Staircase
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Balcony
- 5 - Toilet
- 6 - Shower
- 7 - Bedroom
- 8 - Lounge

- Public
- Private
- Bathroom
- Hall/Corridor
- Balcony/Courtyard
- Circulation (public)
- Circulation (private)
- Circulation (exterior)

Scale 1/200

OVERSCHIE

1957

Interbau Tower, Hansaviertel, Berlin, (1957)
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jo_van_den_Broek
 [10.2008]

'Housing cell' designed to be versatile

The bathroom is divided in toilet, shower and sink (one on each room) in order to allow simultaneous use of the facilities

The shower is accessible directly through the bedrooms

The toilet is accessible through the all so visitors can use it too

The master bedroom can be used as an extension of the living room

The entrance, trough a big sliding door, is made by the living room

The obtained circulation scheme allows to cross the entire apartment

The shower's double access makes possible this circular movement

It simultaneous reinforces and minimizes the apartment functionalist solution

Some practical aspects

Kitchen balcony

Big closet space in the hall, despite te apartment's small areas

VAN DEN BROEK + BAKEMA

1898 – 1978 (Jo van den Broek); 1914 – 1981 (Jaap Bakema)

Jaap Bakema and Jo van den Broek
<http://www.team10online.org/team10/bakema/index.html>
 [10.2008]

Dutch architects

Bakema is invited by van den Broek to work at 'Brinkman - van den Broek' in 1948

He had work before in Amsterdam's and Rotterdam's City Hall

First in Urban Development in Amsterdam

Then for Rotterdam's Housing Public Agency

They became 'van den Broek e Bakema' after Brinkman's death

They are considered Modern Movement' main characters ¹, but Bakema participated actively in its revision, trough his participation in the CIAM meetings

Belonged to CIAM's dutch delegation

Prepares the 10th Congress with those who would become members of the TEAM 10

He was the editor of the 'Forum' magazine, used as a platform of the group's ideas

Bakema defines architecture as a comprehensive discipline, called 'Architeturbanism'

Applies the idea of 'neighborhood scale' in the planning of urban functions

His television program 'From the chair to the city: a history of people and space' was a manifesto of his ideas

One of their most visible project was the housing tower in the 1957 Interbau, a 'punkthochhäuser', a low-rise buildings with 4 facades typical of Nordic postwar planning

They had earlier won projection with the Lijnbaan Shopping Center

Their biggest reference remains the Faculty of Architecture of Delft

Bakema would be a teacher there, as in Hamburg

¹ <http://www.answers.com/topic/van-den-broek-bakema-2>, [10.2008]

CAPTIONS

T3 apartment

- 1 - Public Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Lounge
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - WC
- 8 - Bathroom
- 9 - Bedroom

Scale

1/200

Project **UNITÉ D'HABITATION DE NANTES**

Location Nantes (France)
 Author Le Corbusier
 Date 1952-1953
 Promoter Private - Housing Cooperative

original drawing:

Association of the cell Free-standing structure
 Access Inner Gallery
 Type T5, T3, T1, studio...

TYPE-APARTMENT **Area (m2)** **Zone** **Total**

Type **T3**

Gross Floor Area 103,8
 Floor Area 74,8 82,9%

Public Spaces

Lounge	13,0	76,5%	17,4%
(balcony)	5,4		5,2%
Kitchen	4,0	23,5%	5,3%
(counter)	2,5	62,5%	
Total	17,0	100,0%	22,7%

Private Spaces

Bedroom	12,1	35,5%	16,2%
Bedroom	11,0	32,3%	14,7%
(balcony)	2,9		2,8%
Bedroom	11,0	32,3%	14,7%
(balcony)	2,9		2,8%
Total	34,1	100,0%	45,6%

Other Areas

Bathroom	3,0	81,1%	4,0%
WC	0,7	18,9%	0,9%
Total	3,7	100,0%	4,9%

Hall	2,6	13,0%	3,5%
(closet)	0,3	11,5%	
Corridor	1,5	7,5%	2,0%
Stairs	2,0	10,0%	2,7%
Corridor	13,9	69,5%	18,6%
(armários)	2,3	16,5%	
Total	20,0	100,0%	26,7%

Total Floor Area **74,8** **100,0%**

Total (balconies) **11,2** **10,8%**

Typical Unité d'Habotation kitchen, designed by Charlotte Perriand

<http://homedesign.wordpress.com/2009/03/01/palladio-and-le-corbusier/>
 [03.2009]

<http://www.an-architecture.com/2008/11/cloning-buildings.html>
 [03.2009]

association of the cell:

CAPTIONS

T3 apartment

- 1 - Public Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Lounge
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - WC
- 8 - Bathroom
- 9 - Bedroom

- Public
- Private
- Bathroom
- Hall/Corridor
- Balcony/Courtyard
- Circulation (public)
- Circulation (private)
- Circulation (exterior)

Scale 1/200

UNID. HAB. NANTES

1952 - 1953

'Maison Citrohan', 1922
<http://www.freewebs.com/b1223682/fascinatie.htm/>
 [03.2009]

Smaller area than in the Unité d'Habitation de Marseille: 104m²

The double-height living room is missing
 More area for the public areas...
 ..who are now in a single floor

Corridors have more area: 20m² (+3)
 Although the lower dept of the cell...
 ... manifested in the bedrooms' dept

The absence of the double-height makes the space more coherent
 The master bedroom is no longer open to the living room

According to a functionalist scheme the cell presents some deviations
 Bedrooms with a double function, through the sliding doors
 The corridor could accommodate a supplemental use?
 Presents a vaste area...
 ...possibly added to the bedrooms?

LE CORBUSIER

1887 - 1965

<http://www.worshipworthy.com/blog/2009/02/25/bad-ass-from-paris-raphael-young-by-cody-ross/>
 [03.2009]

'Chaise-long Le Corbusier'
<http://confluence.rave.ac.uk/confluence/pages/recentlyupdated.action?key=%7E95248306&maxRecentlyUpdatedPageCount=20>
 [03.2009]

Swiss architect, urban planner, painter, sculptor e writer, with French citizenship

Like many other contemporary architects (like Mies...) he has a rather reduced education
 Studies 'Arts and Crafts' in his hometown, with the architecture professor Charles L'Éplattenier, who influences his early work.

Advocated a nationalist romanticism ornate, supported by local cottage industry

Performs numerous trips abroad, collecting what he considered 'essential and timeless'

The Charterhouse of Ema, Italy, as an image of their socio-political concerns ...

... And the Greek temples, which praises the proportional system, reproduced in 'Modulor'

Works with Auguste Perret, a pioneer of the use of concrete in France ...

... And Peter Behrens, a representative of the German Werkbund

In his office works with Mies van der Rohe and Walter Gropius

By their influence, adopts a theory and a language based on industrial production

Corbusier and the painter Ozenfant nominate it 'purism'

Close to 'Cubism', simplifying its expressionist character

In the 'L'Esprit Nouveau' magazine publishes his opinions, grouped in 'Vers une Architecture'

Summarizes new architecture in 5 points, based on the technical possibilities of concrete

The Villa Savoye and the Housing Units are its ultimate expression, but had already been anticipated by the houses 'Dom-ino' and 'Maison Citrohan' ...

... Stills, open plan, independent façade, big windows, roof gardens

After the 2nd World War abandons the industrial style, exploring the materials' expressiveness

It makes use of concrete marked with the wood of the frameworks in articulated structures

Uses vernacular materials and shapes, more sculptural

The Chapel of Ronchamp is a symbol of this period

In Urbanism reflects the need to rethink the traditional city

Considered unhealthy and inappropriate to the new requirements ...

... Including car traffic, whose influence is the first to recognize

His first urban project was the 'Contemporary City for 3,000,000 inhabitants'

Functional division between trade, housing and industry, separated by green areas

Applied to the 'Plan Voisin' for Paris, which included the demolition of part of the city center

More realistic was the 'Radiant City' of 1933-1935

Large blocks arranged in large venues, like the Housing Units

Has also recurring activity advertising Modern Architecture

Publishes numerous books, pamphlets, posters ...

He is a founding member of CIAM (International Congresses of Modern Architecture)

They tried to link the economic and political spheres to the field of architecture

The 1933 'Charter of Athens' debated the role of urban planning in society

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Outside Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Living/Dining Room
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - Bathroom
- 8 - Bedroom

Scala

1/200

Project		GOLDEN LANE ESTATE		
Location	London (United Kingdom)			
Author	Chanberlin, Powell e Bom			
Date	1952			
Promoter	Public (for City workers)			
Association of the cell	Free-standing structure			
Access	Outside Corridor			
Type	T2 e T3			
TYPE-APARTMENT	Area (m2)	Zone	Total	
Type	T2			
Gross Floor Area	72,9			
Floor Area	59,1			91,5%
Public Spaces				
Lounge	18,6	76,9%		31,5%
(balcony)	5,8			8,0%
Kitchen	5,6	23,1%		9,5%
(cabinet)	1,1	19,6%		
(counter)	2,3	41,1%		
Total	24,2	100,0%		40,9%
Private Spaces				
Bedroom	11,8	50,2%		20,0%
(closet)	1,1	9,3%		
Bedroom	11,7	49,8%		19,8%
(balcony)	1,8			2,5%
(closet)	1,1	9,4%		
Total	23,5	100,0%		39,8%
Other Areas				
Bathroom	3,3			5,6%
Hall	2,1	25,9%		3,6%
Stairs	3,2	39,5%		5,4%
Corridor	2,8	34,6%		4,7%
(closet)	0,4	14,3%		
Total	8,1	100,0%		13,7%
Total (closet/cabinet space)	3,7			6,3%
Total Floor Area	59,1			100,0%
Total (balconies)	7,6			10,4%

original drawing:

<http://www.building.co.uk/story.asp?sectioncode=555&storycode=3133863&c=3>
[04.2009]

<http://www.exhibit-goldenlane.com/2008/07/10/259/>
[04.2009]

association of the cell:

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Outside Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Living/Dining Room
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - Bathroom
- 8 - Bedroom

- Public
- Private
- Bathroom
- Hall/Corridor
- Balcony/Courtyard
- Circulation (public)
- Circulation (private)
- Circulation (exterior)

Scala 1/200

GOLDEN LANE ESTATE 1952

'New Hall College, Cambridge'
1962-66

http://www.vitruvius.com.br/arquitxtos/arq047/arq047_01_e.asp
[04.2009]

Small areas, yet 'spacious-looking'¹
 Double-height living room and elegant stairs
 Window between the kitchen and living room
 Also a double-height balcony
 Reminiscences of Le Corbusier's 'Housing Units'

Common in duplexes, the distribution of area between public and private sectors comes from the separation by floors

Rooms with generous areas with almost 12m²
 Living room with 'only' 19m² and a 'functionalist' kitchen with 5,6m²
 Although open, the space under the stairs is not usable

Given the small areas, there is a concern with storage spaces
 Kitchen, corridor and bedrooms with closets

CHAMBERLIN, POWELL & BON

1920 – 1999 (Geoffrey Chamberlin); 1919 – 1978 (Peter 'Joe' Powell); 1919 – 1978 (Christoph Bom)

'Barbican Estate', 1965-76
<http://www.flickr.com/photos/suburban/1697819929/>
 [04.2009]

British architects and teachers

Society created for development of the 1st award winning Golden Lane Estate project
 They all individually competed, but had agreed to jointly develop the winning design

Regarded as the first representatives of British Modernism

Although they are also considered as 'brutalistas'
 The use of concrete, present in the Barbican Estate, must have greatly contributed

Very influenced by the ideas of Le Corbusier

Their urban planning concept was close to the 'Ville Radieuse'
 The Golden Lane planning, a urban microcosm with all the necessary infrastructures, born in a war destroyed space, has a lot in common
 There are also comparisons between the Golden Lane 'duplexes' and Le Corbusier's 'Unité d'Habitation' cells
 The positioning of the staircase and high ceilings are similar to Nantes

The influence of 'Architectural Review' magazine from the 40 / 50s is also strong

Dominated by a group of artists led by Gordon Cullen, a great proponent of the concept of 'Townscape' through publishing
 'Is the art of making the maze of buildings, streets and spaces that make up the urban environment visually coherent and organized'²

Architecture teachers at the Polytechnic of Kingston, later university

¹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Golden_Lane_Estate, [04.2009]

² http://www.almedina.net/catalog/product_info.php?products_id=4429, [04.2009]

CAPTIONS

Prototype

- 1 - Hall
- 2 - WC
- 3 - Corridor
- 4 - Stairs
- 5 - Closet
- 6 - Living/Dining Room
- 7 - Kitchen
- 8 - Corridor
- 9 - Bedroom
- 10 - Bathroom

Scale

1/200

original drawing:

Project	PROTOTYPE		
Location	(virtual project)		
Author	Alexander Klein		
Date	(no date)		
Promoter	(virtual project)		
Association of the cell	Row Houses		
Access	Direct		
Type	T3 (three-bedroom)		
Groundfloor	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T3		
Gross Floor Area	66,7		
Floor Area	52,8		79,2%
Public Sapces			
Lounge	17,3	86,5%	32,8%
Kitchen	2,7	13,5%	5,1%
(counter)	1,4	51,9%	
Total	20,0	100,0%	37,9%
Private Spaces			
Bedroom	13,0	61,9%	24,6%
Bedroom	4,0	19,0%	7,6%
Bedroom	4,0	19,0%	7,6%
Total	21,0	100,0%	39,8%
Oother Areas			
Bathroom	2,5	73,5%	4,7%
WC	0,9	26,5%	1,7%
Total	3,4	100,0%	6,4%
Hall	1,0	11,9%	1,9%
Corridor	2,6	31,0%	4,9%
Stairs	2,9	34,5%	5,5%
Corridor	1,9	22,6%	3,6%
(closet)	0,3	15,8%	
Total	8,4	100,0%	15,9%
Total Floor Area	52,8	100,0%	

Klein, Alexander
 "Vivienda Mínima, 1906 - 1957", 1980
 Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A.

association of the cell:

CAPTIONS

Prototype

- 1 - Hall
- 2 - WC
- 3 - Corridor
- 4 - Stairs
- 5 - Closet
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- 10 - Bathroom

- Public
- Private
- Bathroom
- Hall/Corridor
- Balcony/Courtyard
- Circulation (public)
- Circulation (private)
- Circulation (exterior)

Scale 1/200

PROTOTYPE

(no date)

Kitchen inspired in models created by Alexander Klein
<http://www.maximainteriores.xl.pt/decor/interiores/1103/casas/a01-00-00.shtml>
 [10.2008]

Two storey row house prototype with only 53m² of usable area, with three bedrooms for three beds

Despite the minimum area, it is still capable of providing privacy for most rooms...

It has a first hall that protects the rest of the house from prying eyes

Gives access to the toilet, separated from the rest of the bathroom

...but in the upper floor, where it is tried to save area in corridors, it's used a compromise solution. One of the bedrooms is only accessible through the bathroom, while the contiguous one has its access in the corridor

Each of these bedrooms has only 4m²...
 ...while the master bedroom has 13m², about 62% of the private areas

ALEXANDER KLEIN

1879 – 1961

<http://www.ikg.uni-karlsruhe.de/projekte/exilarchitekten/architekten/klein.htm>
 [10.2008]

Russian Architect

Studies at the Institute of Engineering S. Petersburg, where he received a classical education

Arts, symmetry, balance and orthodoxy¹

His early works reveal a neo-classical 'opulent, almost ostentatious'²

The design of the Hospital S. Petersburg, design in collaboration, is an example

The type of research he undertakes is intellectually inserted into Modernism

However, it is ignored by the 'modesty of his works in the purely formal field'³

It was only in Berlin, in the 1920's, that he came in contact with the 'New Objectivity' (Neue Sachlichkeit)

His floor plans adopt a 'scientific' scheme, although the building's image was still vaguely neo-classical

His floor plans method of evaluation and development is published in 1927

Aimed at the design of new projects, but also possible for the evaluation of existing buildings. It is organized into three distinct phases:

Comparison of variables such as number of beds, floor area, private and public areas

Relates depth and size of the facade, and their effects on health and cost

Drawing circulation schemes, furniture-free areas, projection of shadows...

Publishes 'Das Einfamilienhaus – Stüttyp', The first volume of a never completed encyclopedia he intended to issue

In Israel, where lives from 1935, he works in various areas

Plan designer in the development of several cities, including a garden city

Counselor and planner for the 'Jewish National Fund for Construction'

Founder, in 1943, of the 'Research Institute of Construction and Planning Problems'

He taught at various institutions throughout his life

Professor in the Faculty of Architecture of S. Petersburg

Project supervision teacher in Berlin

Professor at the School of Charlottenburg

Professor and Director of the School of Architecture at the Technion, Haifa

¹ Rossari, Augusto – 'Os estudos de Alexander Klein e o movimento Racionalista', Klein, Alexander – 'Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957', Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980

² <http://www.answers.com/topic/alexander-klein-1>, [10.2008]

³ Rivolta, Matilde Baffa, - 'Alexander Klein e o problema da casa na Alemanha de Weimar', 'Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957', Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980